

minimal lag time (Jones et al 1984). All control parameters use proportional-integral (PI) algorithms, and a feed-forward algorithm based on PPFD is used to minimize lag effects. The control performance, based on 5-min averages, is usually within 0.25 °C for dry bulb temperature, 0.5 °C for dew point, and 5 µL/L, for CO₂ concentration. The errors are 2-3 times higher on a 2-s basis. An example of control for highly variable PPFD is illustrated in Figure 1. The daytime PPFD levels are shown in Figure 2. Both nighttime venting and venting due to low PPFD are evident.

Gas measurements (CO₂, N₂O, CH₄) use a common sampling system with infrared gas analyzers (IRGAs) and a gas chromatograph (GC). Chamber gas (pressurized, heated, dehumidified) is circulated through polypropylene lines between each chamber and the control building. There are two additional lines for ambient air and calibration gases (N₂O, CH₄). Each chamber has its own CO₂ IRGA (Siemens, Ultramat 22P) while the N₂O IRGA (CID, CI350) and GC (Varian Aerograph 2400) are shared among chambers. Dry bulb temperature is measured with an aspirated, shielded, thermocouple while canopy temperature is monitored with an infrared sensor (Everest Interscience 4000DL). Dew point is monitored using a dew point hygrometer (Dew-10, General Eastmen Instruments) and evapotranspiration or condensate rate is measured by a tipping bucket rain gauge. The CO₂ injection rate is monitored by the mass flow controller and leakage rates are determined from N₂O loss curves. Ambient PPFD is measured with radiometer (Eppley 8-48) using a factor for PPFD.

Data collection and calculations. The carbon exchange rate is calculated from the change in CO₂ concentration and CO₂ injection rate, then corrected for leakage. Tipping bucket rate and calibrated volume per tip are used to compute ET. Other continuous measurements include dew point; dry bulb; soil (or ricefield water); canopy temperatures; ambient CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ concentrations; and PPFD. (See Figures 1 and 2 for examples of measurements.) Leaf photosynthesis and light interception are measured

weekly using a small access door fitted with a body glove. Other weekly plant measurements include development, biomass, leaf area, leaf N, carbohydrate, and Rubisco activity levels using minimal sample sizes. Root length density is measured at the end of the season.

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Environmental factors affecting rice responses to elevated carbon dioxide concentrations

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Enriched CO₂ levels improved crop growth and yield, with a range of responses depending on species and other environmental factors (Kimball 1983). The combined effects of CO₂ and other environmental factors on crops must be clarified to assess the impact of global climate change in different regions and under different crop management conditions. We conducted this study to determine the combined effects of CO₂, temperature, and N level on dry matter production of rice under different radiation and underground environments by using the newly developed temperature gradient tunnel (TGT) (Horie et al 1991).

Rice cultivar Akihikari was grown to maturity in two TGTs for three cropping seasons (1990-92). Air was ventilated through the long axis of the TGT (25 x 2.5 x 1.7 m) during the day; the direction of air flow was reversed at night. The TGT provided a temperature gradient along the long axis for solar radiation during the day and natural cooling of the heat produced by an oil heater at night. The temperature difference between the air inlet and outlet was maintained at about 4 °C throughout the growth period while maintaining natural daily and seasonal variations. The daytime CO₂ in one TGT was kept at ambient level (350 ppm) in all three seasons, and the level in the other at about twice the ambient level (840 ppm in 1990 and 690 ppm in 1991 and 1992).

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Rice plants in 1990 and 1991 were raised in 1/5000a Wagner's pots and spaced evenly in the TGTs; those in 1992 were raised on the ground in TGTs in an underground condition similar to that in a field. Pots in 1990 were rotated twice a week to give the same environment to each plant, while those in 1991 were fixed. The edges of the rice populations in 1991 and 1992 were shaded to create a canopy condition and lessen radiation penetration.

Three N plots (0.3, 1.2, 2.4 g N/pot in 1990 and 1991, and 4, 12, 20 g N/m² in 1992) were created at each of four distances from the air inlet in TGTs. The N levels in 1991 could be converted into 6, 24, and 48 g N/m² by considering the pot density of 20 pots/m².

Air temperature at four distances from the air inlet was measured during the growth period. Crop dry weight and leaf area were periodically measured.

CO₂ effects on isolated plants. The plants in the 1990 experiment were subjected to a radiation environment similar to that for an isolated plant. Figure 1 shows the percent increase in total dry weight at maturity in 1990 for doubled CO₂ (840 ppm) treatment over the ambient CO₂ control as a function of N rate and temperature. The increase ranged from 10 to 122%, with a longer increase at high temperature at all N levels. This is consistent with the results of Imai et al (1985). While nearly doubled CO₂ did not produce any significant effects on leaf area at heading in the low and intermediate N levels, it gave appreciable effects at high N levels, especially under higher temperature regimes (18% increase at 29.50 °C and 43% increase at 30.5 °C). These results suggest that nearly doubled CO₂ raised the optimum temperature for photosynthesis.

1. Percent increase in total dry weight of rice at maturity for doubled CO₂ (840 ppm) treatment over the ambient CO₂ control as a function of N rate and temperature averaged over the growth period. Pot experiment, 1990.

2. Relative responses of crop dry weight at maturity under doubled CO₂ as a function of N level. Vertical bars indicate the standard deviation calculated using the data obtained under 4 temperature regimes.

Increase in crop dry weight by doubling CO₂ was higher at higher N and higher temperatures due to increases in both leaf area and photosynthetic rate.

CO₂ effects on plants in a community. The results obtained in 1991 and 1992, when plants were maintained under canopy conditions, were different from the results with single plants. No consistent trend could be seen in the temperature effects on rice response to the elevated CO₂ under canopy conditions, as was reported in an earlier study (Horie

1993). The average values of relative increases in crop dry weight by doubling CO₂ across temperature treatments as a function of N application rate were plotted in Figure 2. The relative increase was greater at higher N levels and reached a maximum at around 24 g N/m². CO₂ had little effect on leaf area at heading for all N × temperature plots. The enhancement rates of crop dry weight at maturity obtained from pot experiments were much lower than those of field experiments.

When collecting data to assess impact of global climate change on the rice crop, experiments should be done under canopy conditions and underground environments similar to those of field conditions. By analyzing data from long-term CO₂ enrichment experiments on rice, which satisfy these conditions (our TGT experiments and Baker et al 1990), Horie (1993) concluded that the relative increase in rice dry weight by doubling CO₂ was

24%, being less affected by temperature. Our analysis indicates that this enhancement in total dry weight by doubling CO₂ increases with increased N levels up to 30% at optimum N level.

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Responses of rice to elevated levels of carbon dioxide

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Rice is the major crop in China in terms of cultivated area and total yield. The aim of this study was to determine the effects of elevated levels of CO₂ concentration on a Chinese rice variety, Aixiangnuo, and to generate basic parameters for developing global change-crop reaction models.

The experiments were conducted at the Botanical Garden of the Institute of Botany in 1993-94. Ambient or CO₂-enriched (plus 350 ppm CO₂) air was introduced through the bottom of cylindrical open-top chambers (2.2 m diam × 1.7 m tall) with aluminum frames

covered by polyethylene film. Ventilation rate of the chamber was maintained at 3 exchanges/min throughout the growing season. Rice was planted in fertile soil in pots (25 cm diameter × 30 cm tall), and a 3-5 cm water depth was maintained.

The dry matter partitioning in the young seedlings under elevated CO₂ levels was measured (Table 1). Total dry weight increased by 15%, compared with seedlings grown under ambient atmospheric condition. Shoot dry weight increased only 4%, but with the major increase in dry matter occurring in the roots. Elevated CO₂ influences C metabolism and dry matter partitioning between shoots and roots in the rice plant even at early growth stages.

Elevated CO₂ also affected growth at maturity: compared with the control,

Table 1. Influences of CO₂ enrichment on dry matter (mg) partitioning between shoots and roots in 3-4 leaf stage rice seedlings.

Treatment	Whole seedling		Shoot		Root		Root:Shoot	
	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Ratio	(%)
Ambient air	24.7	100	18.4	100	6.3	100	0.34	100
Ambient air plus 350 ppm CO ₂	28.5	115	19.1	104	9.4	149	0.49	